

IMPROVING INTERFACIAL STRESS TRANSFER IN GLASS FIBER POLYMER COMPOSITES THROUGH GRAPHITE NANOPATELETS

Alessandro Pegoretti¹, Diego Pedrazzoli^{1,2} and Kyriaki Kalaitzidou^{2,3}

¹Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Trento
Via Sommarive 9, 38123 Trento, Italy

Email: Alessandro.Pegoretti@unitn.it, web page: <http://www.ing.unitn.it/~pegorett/>

²G. W. Woodruff School of Mechanical Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology
801 Ferst Drive, Atlanta, GA 30332-0405, USA

Email: diego.pedrazzoli@case.edu, web page: http://engineering.case.edu/groups/mst/diego_pedrazzoli

³School of Materials Science and Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology
771 Ferst Drive, Atlanta, GA 30332-0245, USA

Email: kyriaki.kalaitzidou@me.gatech.edu, web page: <http://www.me.gatech.edu/faculty/kalaitzidou>

Keywords: Multi-scale composites, Hybrid composites, Graphite, Interface/Interphase, Mechanical properties, Rheology

ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the effects of graphite nanoplatelets (GNP) melt-dispersed in polymer composites reinforced with glass fibers (GF). Both a thermoplastic and a thermosetting matrix, specifically isotactic polypropylene (PP) and an epoxy resin, were used to prepare hybrid composites. The experimental analysis was conducted at various scale levels. In a preliminary step, interfacial shear strength (ISS) was firstly evaluated on model single-fiber microcomposites. In particular, the effects of GNP addition, either within the matrix or as a coating on the GF, on the fiber-matrix adhesion was investigated by micromechanical tests such as fragmentation and microdebonding. Furthermore, morphological features and mechanical/viscoelastic properties of real composites containing up to 30 wt% of short GF fiber were measured as a function of the amount of GNP dispersed in the polymer matrix.

The incorporation of GNP, either within the matrix or as a coating of the GF, was found to promote the formation of a stronger fiber/matrix interface, resulting in a ISS increase of 59% in case of the epoxy system containing 5 wt% of GNP and coated GF. An improvement of the fiber-matrix adhesion was also observed on polypropylene-based composites: ISS values increased up to a factor of about 6 for a 7 wt% content of GNP. Mechanical tests indicated that the stronger interfacial strength observed in hybrid composites leads to an increased elastic modulus without compromising the impact strength, concurrently with significantly improved viscoelastic behaviour. Therefore, this study revealed that the combined effect of nano-materials and micro-size reinforcements can be exploited to produce lightweight hybrid composites with enhanced mechanical properties, without compromising their processability in comparison to GF/PP composites, as indicated by rheological measurements.

1 INTRODUCTION

As widely reported in the current literature, the introduction of small amounts of nanomaterials (< 10 wt%) in polymeric matrices (either thermoplastics or thermosettings) can remarkably increase their mechanical properties and thermal stability [1], dramatically enhance the electrical [2] and thermal [3] conductivity of the resulting composites and play a beneficial role on the interfacial properties of structural composites [4]. Loading of more than 10 wt% nanomaterials in polymers is usually associated to poor dispersion, difficult processability [5], and increased cost and density of the composite. Quite on the contrary, fiber loadings of 30-50 wt% are commonly used in the industry to realize fiber-reinforced light-weight structural components. However, because short-fiber reinforced composites are less strong than the corresponding continuous-fiber-reinforced composites, it is of great

interest to explore whether combining two fillers of rather different size scales (i.e. micro- and nano-scale) would give the desired performances at low to intermediate filler loadings [6].

Therefore, the aim of this study is to investigate how the morphology and the mechanical properties of short-glass fiber reinforced composites are affected by the presence of a carbonaceous nanofiller namely, graphite nanoplatelets (GNP). In order to evaluate the effect of filler incorporation on the mechanical behavior of polymeric matrices with different morphology and inherent mechanical properties, both polypropylene (PP) and an epoxy resin were used to fabricate the composites. The role of the fiber-matrix adhesion on the quasi-static, viscoelastic and impact properties of the resulting materials was investigated in hybrid composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials and fabrication of composites

An isotactic homopolymer polypropylene with the trade name PPH-B-10-FB (MFI at 190 °C and 2.16 kg = 6.9 g/10', density = 0.904 g/cm³) produced by Polychim Industrie s.a.s. (Loon-Plage, France) was used. Fusabond[®] P M-613-05 maleic anhydride modified polypropylene, PPgMA, (MFI=106.8 g/10' at 190 °C and 2.16 kg, 0.903 g/cm³, maleic anhydride content = 0.35 - 0.70 wt%), by DuPont[™] was used as compatibilizer. Exfoliated graphite nanoplatelets xGnP[®] - M5 from XG Science Inc., with an average diameter of ~5 µm and thickness in the range of 10~20 nm were used. E-glass fibers, RO99 P319, by Saint-GobainVetrotex, were used as-received. The GF are surface treated with a silane based coupling agent. Chopped strand GF (single fiber diameter of 15.3 ± 1.5 µm, and average length of 6.50 ± 0.44 mm) were obtained by chopping long GF using a chopper gun. Graphite-coated GF were prepared by sonication of GNP in isopropanol at a concentration of 5 mg/ml using a Misonix S-4000-010 for 1 h (30% amplitude, 8 W power) equipped with a probe of 12.5 mm diameter. After adding the GF to the solution, sonication was continued for 0.5 h. The GNP-coated GF were rinsed in isopropanol and dried under hood overnight. The GNP content of the coated GF was ~ 0.10-0.15 wt% with respect to the composite's weight.

Polypropylene composites were made by melt mixing and injection molding using a vertical, co-rotating, bench-top twin-screw micro-extruder (DSM Micro 15 cm³ Compounder) connected to a micro-injection molding unit (DSM). The compound was mixed for 3 min, at 190 °C and 250 rpm. After the polymer compound had melted and homogenized, short GF strands were added to the melt and further mixed for 2 min before injection molding. The mold temperature was 80 °C and the injection pressure was 800 KPa. The PPgMA was added at 1:1 ratio with respect to the GNP.

A bicomponent epoxy resin, consisting of 635 thin epoxy and a 556 slow amminic hardener at a weight ratio of 2:1, was supplied by US Composites (West Palm Beach, FL). Epoxy composites were made as follows: first the GNP were dispersed in isopropanol by sonication using the same conditions as mentioned above for GNP-coated GF. Once the isopropanol was filtered away, the GNP powder was mixed with the epoxy at 800 rpm and T=60 °C for 40 min using a magnetic stirring plate. The GF were then added to the solution and stirring was continued for 20 min followed by addition of the curing agent and subsequent stirring at 800 rpm for 30 min. The mixture was degassed in a vacuum oven and cured in a mold at T=80 °C for 1h, followed by post-curing at T=100 °C for 4h.

Polypropylene composites are designated as follows: the kind of filler with its content, the compatibilizer (if any) with its content and the matrix. For instance, the composite filled with 5 wt% of PPgMA, 5 wt% of xGnP-M5 and 10 wt% GF was indicated as 5GNP/10GF/5PPgMA/PP. Coated GF are indicated as GFc. Epoxy composites were designated by the amount and type of the filler, for example the composite containing 5 wt% of xGnP-M5 and 10 wt% GF is indicated as 5GNP/10GF/epoxy.

2.2 Experimental techniques

The effect of the GNP on the fiber-matrix adhesion, was investigated through microdebonding tests on specimens consisting of a polymer microdrop solidified onto a single fiber filament supported on a paper tab. Polymer microdrops were distributed symmetrically around the filament operating under an optical microscope. Noteworthy, epoxy drops were cured for 1h at 80 °C followed by 4h at 100 °C.

Prior to testing, the samples were examined using an optical microscope in order to determine the fiber diameter (d), embedded fiber length (L), and the maximum droplet diameter (D). Microdebonding tests were conducted at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min by an Instron 33R 4466 tensile tester equipped with a 500 N load cell. During testing the paper tab attached to one end of the glass fiber was slowly pulled up, while the droplet was constrained by a shearing plate, fixed on a stationary support. The interfacial shear strength (ISS) was computed by equation (1):

$$ISS = \frac{F_c}{\pi dL} \quad (1)$$

where F_c is the critical applied load, recorded during the test, at which the fiber-matrix interface fails. The single fiber specimens were observed by SEM before and after the test.

The fracture surface of the composites was studied using a Phenom G2 Pro (Phenom-World BV) scanning electron microscope (SEM), at an acceleration voltage of 5 kV. A thin gold coating was applied onto the surface by plasma sputtering to minimize the charging effects. The rheological behavior of the composites was analyzed by an ARES-G2 rheometer (TA Instruments) under controlled strain conditions using parallel plate geometry. The test specimens were disks with a diameter of 25 mm. Isothermal frequency sweep tests were carried out in the range 0.1–200 rad/s using a small amplitude (10%) oscillatory shear. Each data point is an average of three measurements. Tensile tests were performed according to ASTM D638 with an Instron model 33R 4466 tensile tester equipped with a 10 kN load cell at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min. Each data point is an average of at least five measurements. Axial strain was recorded by using a resistance extensometer Instron[®] model 2630-101 with a gauge length of 10 mm. The elastic modulus was measured as a secant value between longitudinal deformations of 0.05 % and 0.25 %. Dynamic mechanical thermal analyses (DMTA) in tensile mode were carried out using a DMA Q800 (TA Instruments) over a temperature range of 20 to 160 °C, at a heating rate of 5 °C/min and a frequency of 1 Hz. A pre-stress of 0.2 MPa and a maximum strain of 0.05 % were imposed on rectangular samples 25 mm long, 3.30 mm wide and 3.27 mm thick. Impact tests (Izod type) were performed according to ASTM D256 standard, by a mechanical pendulum provided by Custum Scientific Intruments, Inc.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Interfacial shear strength

The incorporation of GNP in PP matrix results in a remarkable increase of the shear strength evaluated at the interface (ISS), indicating a substantial enhancement of the load transfer between fiber and matrix (Figure 1a). Interestingly, the greatest improvement is achieved in the compatibilized system (i.e. 5GNP/GF/5PPgMA/PP), with a clear synergistic effect of PPgMA and nanofiller. In particular, PPgMA is supposed not only to improve the nanofiller dispersion, but also to significantly enhance the chemical affinity between PP and GNP and between PP and GF [7]. Noteworthy, a slightly enhanced ISS can also be noticed when coated GF were used (i.e. GFc/PP and 5GNP/GFc/PP), indicating a positive effect of the GNP fiber coating on the interfacial interactions.

In a similar way to PP composites, the introduction of GNP in the epoxy matrix results in a dramatic increase of the ISS evaluated at the interface (Figure 1b). Values of interfacial resistance confirm the superior tensile and viscoelastic properties exhibited by hybrid composites (section 3.3), in particular when considering the ultimate tensile strength and impact resistance. Improved interfacial strengths are also observed when the microdebonding test is performed on the system GFc/epoxy, evidencing the beneficial effect of the fiber coating on the interfacial interactions. However, the best ISS values are obtained when combining nanomodified epoxy with coated fibers (i.e. 5GNP/GFc), showing an improvement of 58.9%.

Figure 1: Interfacial shear strength values of (a) GF/PP composites and (b) GF/epoxy composites as a function of the GNP amount, considering uncoated (full point) and coated (open point) glass fibers. (▲) indicates the system GF/5PPgMA/PP and 5GNP/GF/5PPgMA/PP.

3.2 Morphology characterization

SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces for PP composites loaded with 10 wt% GF are shown in Figure 2a. The glass fibers appear rather homogeneously dispersed in the PP matrix, and several fibers have been pulled out from the matrix, indicating that interfacial debonding was the dominant failure mechanism due to low adhesion levels. However, a different failure behavior is observed for hybrid PP composites containing 5 wt% GNP and 10 wt% GF (Figure 2b) and 5 wt% PPgMA, 5 wt% GNP and 10 wt% GF (Figure 2c). As only few fibers have been debonded, a significantly better fiber-matrix adhesion can be observed and the improved fiber/matrix interaction is evidenced by the presence of matrix residuals on the fiber surface after the pull-out. The effectiveness of the glass fibers coating, when considering the 5GNP/10GFc/PP composite, is indicated by the presence of some graphite residuals on the fiber surface after the pull-out (Figure 2d).

Figure 2: SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces of (a) 10GF/PP, (b) 5GNP/10GF/PP, (c) 5GNP/10GF/5PPgMA/PP and (d) 5GNP/10GFc/PP composites.

Fracture surfaces of epoxy nanocomposites and composites were analyzed and compared to that of neat epoxy (Figure 3a). GNP aggregates with dimension of $\sim 5\text{-}10\ \mu\text{m}$ are quite well distributed within the matrix in the 5GNP/epoxy sample, while most of the graphite aggregates do not seem to be intercalated (Figure 3b). Moreover, when taking into account GF composites, morphological analyses reveal that the glass fibers are generally well dispersed in the unfilled epoxy matrix, and many fibers are pulled out from the matrix (Figure 3c), indicating low-adhesion condition. On the other hand, epoxy matrix additivated with GNP show a different failure behavior (Figure 3d), with fewer fibers pulled out from the matrix and diffuse matrix crack, evidencing a significantly better fiber-matrix adhesion.

Figure 3: SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces of (a) neat epoxy, (b) 5GNP/epoxy, (c) 10GF/epoxy and (d) 5GNP/10GF/epoxy composites.

3.3 Tensile properties of hybrid composites

The tensile modulus (E), tensile strength (σ_B) and strain at break (ε_B) of the hybrid PP composites, as a function of the GNP content, are presented in Table 1a along with the specific modulus (E^*) and the specific tensile strength (σ_B^*). It can be observed that at constant GF content of 10 wt%, the moduli E and E^* significantly increase with GNP content, the σ_B and σ_B^* initially increase reaching a plateau and ε_B decreases with GNP content. The increase of s_B at low and intermediate GNP contents is promoted by the enhancement of the GF/PP interfacial shear strength, making the hybrid composites lighter and stronger than the GF composites. When GNP-coated GF are used (i.e. 10GFc/PP and 5GNP/10GFc/PP composites), the composites exhibit slightly higher E^* and σ_B^* compared to the corresponding composites 10GF/PP and 5GNP/10GF/PP, where the GNP is only added incorporated in the PP matrix, as a result of stronger GF-PP interfacial interactions. A significant increase of σ_B in composites also occurs in composites added with PPgMA compatibilizer, which promotes greater adhesion levels at the fiber-matrix interface.

As reported in Table 1b, E and σ_B of the epoxy increase significantly with GNP content and even more in GF/epoxy composites, while ε_B decreases. The higher σ_B exhibited by the hybrid composites with respect to the σ_B of GF/epoxy composites, reflects the greater interfacial shear strength between fiber and matrix which promotes a better stress transfer across the interface. The superiority of hybrid composites with respect to GF/epoxy composites is even more evident when the specific properties (E^* and σ_B^*) are taken into account. In particular, the σ_B^* of the hybrid composites is remarkably higher than that of GF/epoxy ones. Hybrid composites are thus lighter and stronger than GF reinforced epoxy composites. The mechanical properties are also enhanced when GNP-coated GF are used. Specifically, the properties of the 10GFc/epoxy and 5GNP/10GFc/epoxy composites are better than the properties of the corresponding composites made using the as-received GF, reflecting stronger interfacial interactions and probably better adhesion between the coated GF and the epoxy resin.

<i>Sample</i>	E [MPa] E^* [MPa/(g/cm ³)]	σ_B [MPa] σ_B^* [MPa/(g/cm ³)]	ϵ_B [%]	<i>Izod impact strength</i> [J/m]
PP	2059±84 2278	38.5±0.7 42.6	8.9 ± 0.5	15.8 ± 1.4
30GF/PP	4693±77 4199	43.1±0.7 38.6	2.8 ± 0.2	46.2 ± 2.0
10GF/PP	3208±76 3323	41.8±0.3 43.3	6.3 ± 0.5	34.2 ± 1.8
10GFc/PP	3562±26 3689	41.8±0.3 43.3	5.9 ± 0.1	36.3 ± 1.4
1GNP/10GF/PP	3565±72 3674	43.8±0.4 45.1	4.7 ± 0.2	/
3GNP/10GF/PP	3660±132 3735	43.8±0.4 44.4	4.4 ± 0.2	/
5GNP/10GF/PP	4255±135 4299	43.9±0.1 44.4	3.6 ± 0.1	42.2 ± 2.4
5GNP/10GFc/PP	4472±82 4518	45.4±0.8 45.9	4.1 ± 0.2	45.0 ± 1.9
7GNP/10GF/PP	4431±62 4431	43.7±0.3 43.7	3.6 ± 0.1	/
5GNP/15GF/PP	4670±48 4560	44.8±0.5 43.7	3.6 ± 0.2	46.0 ± 1.6
5GNP/10GF/5PPgMA/PP	4287±93 4331	49.1±0.3 49.6	4.1 ± 0.2	50.0 ± 1.6

Table 1a: Mechanical properties of PP composites.

<i>Sample</i>	E [MPa] E^* [MPa/(g/cm ³)]	σ_B [MPa] σ_B^* [MPa/(g/cm ³)]	ϵ_B [%]	<i>Izod impact strength</i> [J/m]
epoxy	2917 ± 37 (2537)	59.6 ± 0.7 51.8	4.1 ± 0.1	26.5 ± 2.1
5GNP/epoxy	3543 ± 76 (3023)	62.4 ± 0.2 (53.2)	3.5 ± 0.1	28.6 ± 1.4
10GF/epoxy	3793 ± 40 (3122)	63.7 ± 0.3 (52.4)	3.1 ± 0.2	80.5 ± 2.3
30GF/epoxy	4266 ± 80 (3111)	67.8 ± 0.2 (49.5)	2.0 ± 0.2	116.2 ± 2.4
5GNP/10GF/epoxy	3907 ± 74 (3156)	67.0 ± 0.6 (54.2)	3.0 ± 0.2	92.4 ± 1.9
5GNP/15GF/epoxy	4178 ± 91 (3282)	70.4 ± 0.7 (55.3)	2.2 ± 0.2	107.5 ± 1.9
10GFc/epoxy	3818 ± 65 (3140)	64.7 ± 0.2 (53.2)	3.0 ± 0.2	86.4 ± 1.4
5GNP/10GFc/epoxy	3949 ± 47 (3189)	67.9 ± 0.2 (54.8)	2.8 ± 0.2	101.4 ± 1.1

Table 1b: Mechanical properties of epoxy composites.

3.4 Impact strength

The impact resistance increases by more than 10% with the addition of only 5 wt% GNP in PP composites (Table 1a). Noteworthy, the increase in impact resistance can be ascribed to (i) changes in the energy absorbing mechanisms and (ii) different crystalline morphology (i.e. spherulite size and polymorphism) occurring upon nanomodification, while nanofiller agglomeration usually tends to limit the toughening effect in polymer matrices. As expected, the impact resistance increases with the GF loading, while significant improvements can be observed when coated GF are used compared to the systems based on uncoated GF. The enhancement in impact resistance corresponds to 6.1% and 6.6% when 10GFc/PP and 5GNP/10GFc/PP, are considered respectively.

In a similar way, results show that the impact resistance of the epoxy matrix increases with addition of 5 wt% GNP (~ 8%), while a noticeable increase dependent on the GF loading is also obtained in GF/epoxy composites (Table 1b). Owing to the GF surface modification and the beneficial presence of the nanofiller within the matrix, hybrid composites exhibit a considerable improvement in impact strength when compared to non-hybrid composites at the same GF loading, showing a dependence on the GF-epoxy interfacial interactions.

3.5 Viscoelastic behaviour under dynamic shear and tension

The effect of GNP and GF incorporation on the dynamic shear storage modulus (G') and complex viscosity ($|\eta^*|$) of PP as evaluated at melt state, is reported in Figure 4 as a function of frequency at constant temperature.

Figure 4: Complex viscosity $|\eta^*|$ and storage modulus (G') with respect to angular frequency (ω) of PP composites.

As expected, both G' and $|\eta^*|$ significantly increase with the GF loading, while a further increase is noticed upon addition of GNP. Interestingly, the sample 5GNP/15GF/PP exhibits values of viscosity comparable with those of 30GF/PP, indicating that for the same content the nanofiller results in a greater increase in viscosity than GF. The dynamic mechanical properties of the composites were also influenced by the fiber and GNP content (Table 2a). In particular, the storage modulus (E') increases with GF loading, while the loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) decreases. Moreover, the glass transition temperature (T_g), determined as the temperature of the $\tan\delta$ peak, increases also with GNP content, evidencing a secondary reinforcing mechanism of PP promoted by the polymer-GNP physical interactions which alter the mobility of the polymeric chains. In the same way, lower values of $\tan\delta$ recorded upon GNP addition in hybrid composites can be attributed not only to a stiffening effect and the enhanced fiber-

matrix adhesion, but also to polymer-GNP physical interactions, resulting in lower loss modulus and enhanced elastic modulus of PP.

Sample	$E' (-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C})$ [MPa]	$E' (+23\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C})$ [MPa]	T_g [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	$\tan\delta \cdot 10^{-2}$
PP	2971 \pm 14	1479 \pm 11	15.1 \pm 0.1	7.89 \pm 0.11
10GF/PP	4619 \pm 32	2946 \pm 14	16.0 \pm 0.1	6.15 \pm 0.72
30GF/PP	5988 \pm 30	4238 \pm 16	16.1 \pm 0.1	5.21 \pm 0.91
1GNP/10GF/PP	4670 \pm 25	3114 \pm 35	16.2 \pm 0.2	6.03 \pm 0.73
3GNP/10GF/PP	4980 \pm 41	3238 \pm 42	16.2 \pm 0.1	5.94 \pm 0.71
5GNP/10GF/PP	5128 \pm 37	3395 \pm 25	16.9 \pm 0.2	5.88 \pm 0.90
7GNP/10GF/PP	5462 \pm 40	3720 \pm 33	16.9 \pm 0.1	5.75 \pm 0.62
5GNP/15GF/PP	5671 \pm 42	3849 \pm 29	17.0 \pm 0.1	5.41 \pm 0.43
5GNP/10GF/5PPgMA/PP	5231 \pm 27	3434 \pm 21	17.4 \pm 0.1	5.73 \pm 0.54

Table 2a: Viscoelastic properties of PP composites.

The effect of the GF addition on the dynamic shear storage modulus (G') and complex viscosity ($|\eta^*|$) of epoxy composites as a function of frequency is reported in Figures 5a and b respectively. As expected, both G' and $|\eta^*|$ significantly increase with the GF loading across the whole frequency range. Moreover, a further increase is recorded upon incorporation of GNP in the 15GF/epoxy composite. In addition to the frequency sweep, the viscoelastic rheological properties of the composites were also evaluated at two different temperatures, specifically below and above T_g . The results are shown in Figure 5a and Figure 5b, respectively.

Figure 5: (a) Storage modulus (G') and (b) complex viscosity ($|\eta^*|$) with respect to angular frequency (ω) of epoxy composites.

As the temperature increases, both the storage modulus and the viscosity decrease as expected due to polymer chain relaxation at high temperatures [8]. The decrease in the storage modulus above T_g can be ascribed to a transition from elastic-solid to viscous-liquid behavior. Moreover, the 5GNP/15GF/epoxy composite exhibits values of G' comparable with those of 30GF/epoxy (i.e. the typical industrial reference composite), while when the viscosity is taken into account, the hybrid

system shows slightly lower values. Noteworthy, the pinning effect of the nanofiller onto the polymeric chains [9] might also play a key role in increasing the viscosity in hybrid composites. The dynamic mechanical properties of epoxy composites were significantly influenced by the fiber weight fraction: as expected, E' increases with higher GF contents (Table 2b), while $\tan\delta$ decreases. In addition, the incorporation of GNP in the epoxy matrix produces a considerable increase of E' and a concurrent decrease of the loss tangent. Moreover, the glass transition temperature, as evaluated at the $\tan\delta$ peak during DMA experiments, significantly increases in both GNP nanocomposites and GF composites. In particular, the increase in T_g observed in the nanocomposite can be ascribed to a chain-pinning mechanism promoted by polymer-GNP physical interactions. Therefore, as already observed for PP composites, GNP reinforces the host matrix not only because it is stiffer, but also because it remarkably alters locally the physical properties of the polymer. As GNP and GF are filled in the matrix, the synergistic effect of both fillers further reduces molecular motions, and thus enhance the restriction on the rate of relaxation, leading to higher T_g [9].

Sample	E' (25 °C) [MPa]	E' (80 °C) [MPa]	T_g [°C]	$\tan\delta$
epoxy	786 ± 16	6 ± 2	64.8 ± 0.2	1.17 ± 0.06
5GNP/epoxy	862 ± 21	15 ± 3	65.2 ± 0.3	1.07 ± 0.04
10GF/epoxy	1032 ± 29	84 ± 6	66.2 ± 0.2	0.78 ± 0.04
30GF/epoxy	1581 ± 32	161 ± 11	66.8 ± 0.4	0.48 ± 0.08
5GNP/10GF/epoxy	1221 ± 24	119 ± 8	67.7 ± 0.3	0.53 ± 0.06
5GNP/15GF/epoxy	1311 ± 35	138 ± 12	67.7 ± 0.3	0.45 ± 0.04
10GFc/epoxy	1062 ± 20	89 ± 9	66.3 ± 0.2	0.75 ± 0.03
5GNP/10GFc/epoxy	1240 ± 14	122 ± 8	67.9 ± 0.3	0.49 ± 0.04

Table 2b: Viscoelastic properties of epoxy composites.

The storage modulus of the composites is considered below and above T_g (i.e. at $T = 25$ °C and $T = 80$ °C, respectively). As a representative example, the storage modulus of the composite 5GNP/10GF/epoxy, normalized with respect to that of 10GF/epoxy, corresponds to 1.18 and 1.42 when considered below and above T_g , respectively, confirming the chain blocking mechanism due to GNP incorporation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study the effects of GNP incorporation, either within the matrix or as a coating of the GF, on the fiber-matrix adhesion were investigated on GF/polymer microcomposites by microdebonding tests. Both a thermoplastic and thermosetting matrix, specifically PP and an epoxy resin, were used for the sake of comparison to produce the hybrid composites. It was observed that the incorporation of GNP markedly increased the resistance of the fiber-matrix interface, resulting in an increase of the interfacial shear strength (ISS) of 59% in case of the epoxy system incorporating 5 wt% GNP and GNP-coated GF. The greater interfacial strength observed in hybrid composites led to an increased elastic modulus, strength and better viscoelastic behavior without compromising the impact strength, showing that also in the case of a matrix with relatively high stiffness and strength such as the epoxy, the mechanical performances can be greatly enhanced in hybrid composites.

No significant changes in the processability of hybrid composites were observed in comparison to non-hybrid composites. In conclusion, this study revealed that the combined effect of nano-materials and micro-size reinforcements can be exploited to produce lightweight hybrid composites with enhanced mechanical properties, as part of the high density GF can be replaced with a smaller amount of GNP.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Njuguna, K. Pielichowski and J.R. Alcock, Epoxy-based fibre reinforced nanocomposites, *Advanced Engineering Materials*, **9**, 2007, pp. 835-847.
- [2] D. Pedrazzoli D, A. Dorigato and A. Pegoretti, Monitoring the mechanical behaviour under ramp and creep conditions of electrically conductive polymer composites, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **43**, 2012, pp. 1285-1292.
- [3] S. Ganguli, A.K. Roy and D.P. Anderson, Improved thermal conductivity for chemically functionalized exfoliated graphite/epoxy composites, *Carbon*, **46**, 2008, pp. 806-817.
- [4] A. Dorigato, S. Morandi and A. Pegoretti, Effect of nanoclay addition on the fiber/matrix adhesion in epoxy/glass composites, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **46**, 2012, pp. 1439-1451.
- [5] F. Hussain, Review article: Polymer-matrix Nanocomposites, Processing, Manufacturing, and Application: An Overview, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **40**, 2006, pp. 1511-1575.
- [6] W.K. Li, D.L. He and J.B. Bai, The influence of nano/micro hybrid structure on the mechanical and self-sensing properties of carbon nanotube-microparticle reinforced epoxy matrix composite, *Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **54**, 2013, pp. 28-36.
- [7] D. Pedrazzoli and A. Pegoretti, Silica nanoparticles as coupling agents for polypropylene/glass composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **76**, 2013, pp. 77-83.
- [8] M.A. Osman and A. Atallah, Interparticle and particle–matrix interactions in polyethylene reinforcement and viscoelasticity, *Polymer*, **46**, 2005, pp. 9476-9488.
- [9] T. Wan, S. Liao, K. Wang, P. Yan and M. Clifford, Multi-scale hybrid polyamide 6 composites reinforced with nano-scale clay and micro-scale short glass fibre, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **50**, 2013, pp. 31-38.